

A large dataset of software mentions in the biomedical literature

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Abstract

We describe the CZ Software Mentions, a new dataset of software mentions in biomedical papers. Plain-text mentions are extracted with a trained SciBERT model from several sources: the NIH PubMed Central collection and papers provided by various publishers to the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative. The dataset provides sources, context and metadata, and, for a number of mentions, the disambiguated software entities and links. We extract 1.12 million unique string software mentions from 2.4 million papers in the NIH PMC-OA Commercial subset, 481k unique mentions from the NIH PMC-OA Non-Commercial subset and 934k unique mentions from 3 million papers in the Publishers' collection. We propose a clustering-based disambiguation algorithm to map plain-text software mentions into distinct software entities and apply it on the NIH PubMed Central Commercial collection. Through this methodology, we disambiguate 1.12 million unique strings into 97600 unique software entities, covering 78% of all software-paper links. We link 185,000 of the mentions to repositories, covering about 55% of all software-paper links. We describe in detail the process of building the datasets, disambiguating and linking the software mentions. We make all data and code publicly available to help assess the impact of software (in particular scientific open source projects) on science.

Introduction

The common adage says that the work of the scientist is only as good as their tools. Since the last century software has become a key tool in a scientist's toolbox and in recent years some of the most important breakthroughs in science—from the solution of 50-year-old protein folding problem (Jumper et al., 2021) to the first-ever direct image of a black hole's event horizon (Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration, 2022)—have been made possible through advanced computational methods applied to large swaths of data. Yet, identifying and crediting the computational tools that enabled these discoveries, and rewarding their creators, remains a challenge. While there are established norms in science for giving formal citation and credit to the authors of scholarly papers going back centuries, software—as many types of non-traditional research outputs (Alperin, Schimanski, La, Niles, & McKiernan, 2022; Bucknell, 2016; Priem, Taraborelli, Groth, & Neylon, 2010)—is often neglected or treated as a second-class type of output and eminently hard to cite. Not being able to measure the impact of critical software tools that enable scientific progress makes it hard for their authors and maintainers to pursue scientific careers and to obtain funding for their work (Howison & Bullard, 2016; Howison, Deelman, McLennan, Ferreira da Silva, & Herbsleb, 2015; Howison & Herbsleb, 2011; Knowles, Mateen, & Yehudi, 2021; Singh Chawla, 2016). Furthermore, it makes it more difficult for other scientists to reproduce results in scientific papers, and creates barriers for funders who need to objectively evaluate the impact of their support (Howison & Bullard, 2016; Joppa et al., 2013; Mesirov, 2010; Nowogrodzki, 2019; Strasser, Hertweck, Greenberg, Taraborelli, & Vu, 2022).

While these problems have been well recognized (Howison & Bullard, 2016; D. S. Katz et al., 2014), and a number of recommendations for citing software have been published (D. Katz et al., 2021; Smith, Katz, Niemeyer, & FORCE11 Software Citation Working Group, 2016), in

scientific papers software is often only credited with informal mentions and phrases like *for analysis ImageJ software was used*. Until citation practices for software are improved, an analysis of the text of the papers remains necessary in order to get insight into software usage.

The extraction of software mentions from the text of scientific papers has attracted the attention of researchers for quite some time (see the review (Krüger & Schindler, 2020) and the recent publications (Lopez, Du, Cohoon, Ram, & Howison, 2021; Orduña-Malea & Costas, 2021)). There are several datasets available, including *SoftwareKG*, a knowledge graph that contains information about software mentions from more than 51000 scientific articles from the social sciences (Schindler, Zapilko, & Krüger, 2020); *SoMeSci*, a curated collection of 3756 software mentions in 1367 PubMed Central articles (Schindler, Bensmann, Dietze, & Krüger, 2021); *Softcite*, a dataset of manual annotations of 4971 academic PDFs in biomedicine and economics (Du, Cohoon, Lopez, & Howison, 2021); (Lopez, Du, Cohoon, & Howison, 2021), a dataset of 318,138 software mentions based on CORN-19 dataset; and (Wade & Williams, 2021), another dataset of 77,449 software mentions based on CORN-19 dataset. These datasets are based on limited samples of scholarly articles. A paper based on a similar approach (Schindler, Bensmann, Dietze, & Krüger, 2022) was published while this preprint was in preparation. Similarly to our work, it is based on Pubmed Central Open Access dataset. The methodology for software extraction is similar and based on SciBERT (Beltagy, Lo, & Cohan, 2019). The paper uses a hierarchical multi-task labeling model to extract additional tags besides software and the version, such as software type, mention type and additional information. The training corpora for our datasets are different: we trained our model on SoftCite (Du et al., 2021), while Schindler et al. (2022) trained the model on the SoMeSci dataset (Schindler et al., 2021). Our disambiguation methodologies are overall similar and built on clustering algorithms, with differences in the type of features used. There is also a difference in the number of clusters obtained. Our linking methodology is quite different. The authors predict links based on training on the SoMeSci dataset, whereas we predict links by querying a number of repositories on names of clusters obtained through disambiguation. The authors extract 301,825,757 triples describing 11.8M software mentions and construct a knowledge graph based on the results. The sizes of the resulting mention datasets are similar: ours has 19.3M mentions (Table 1). The formats of the final datasets are also different: for example, we provide context for each mention in the dataset. We plan to conduct a more detailed comparison of our results and methods.

In this work we describe a series of larger datasets of software mentions based on (1) the full PubMed Central collection (*PMC Help*, 2005) downloaded in October 2021 containing more than 3.8 million papers (Table 1), and (2) a collection of papers provided by various publishers to the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (Table 2). We use a SciBERT-based model trained on the SoftCite dataset (Du et al., 2021) to extract software mentions from these corpora. There can be large variability in how a software entity is mentioned in text or extracted by the NER model, so we propose a clustering-based technique to disambiguate the plain-text mentions into distinct software entities. We also describe a methodology to link the mentions to PyPI, CRAN, Bioconductor, SciCrunch or GitHub.

We apply the disambiguation and linking methodologies to the PMC-OA *comm* subset, from which the NER model extracts 1.12 million unique string software mentions appeared in 2.4 million papers. We are able to disambiguate 320,000 of these mentions into 97,600 unique software entities, covering about 78% of all links in the dataset. For all the other strings extracted by the NER model, we cannot confidently map them to a software entity through our

methodology. We also link about 185,000 mentions to a repository, covering about 55% of all software-paper links.

We curate a proportion of the final datasets by engaging a domain expert team. Through this process, we find that the precision of the NER model ‘in the wild’, on the top 10000 mentions (by frequency) in the PMC-OA *comm* subset, or Precision@10k is 69.66% (Precision score of the model on the SoftCite dataset is 90%). We describe in detail our methodology and make the final datasets available to the community. We hope this work serves as a resource for assessing the impact of scientific software.

Materials and methods

Full text collection

We used two separate full text collections. The first dataset is based on the PubMed Central collection (*PMC Help*, 2005) (*PMC OA*) downloaded on October 2021. The PMC OA collection has two subsets: *comm* subset licensed for both commercial and non-commercial use, and *non_comm* subset licensed for non-commercial use only, including data mining. We kept these data separate to ensure that our data set can be utilized for both commercial and non-commercial uses (see the discussion of non commercial licensing in (Veytsman, 2021)). The statistics of the data set is shown in Table 2. Second, there were full-text manuscripts of scholarly articles (both Open Access and paywalled manuscripts) provided to the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative by publishers under different agreements (*Publishers’ collection*). This corpus also includes preprints from *bioRxiv*. The provenance and time span of this collection varies (see Table 3). As seen from Tables 2 and 1, the datasets have significant overlap.

The Publishers’ collection was stored in LXML format PMC OA papers were downloaded in NXML format. For parsing LXML we used *lxml* (Behnel, Faassen, & Bicking, 2005); for parsing NXML we used a modified *pubmed_parser* software (Achakulvisut, Acuna, & Kording, 2020). Our modifications concerned table caption extraction (not implemented in the original) and speeding up parsing. They, along with the other modules, are available at the GitHub site accompanying this publication. The extracted text was fed into the SciBERT-based NER model and further processed.

Table 1. PMC OA statistics

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Commercial set</i>	<i>Non-commercial set</i>
Number of papers	2,433,010	1,442,868
Number of papers with at least one mention	1,732,603	758,246
Number of mentions	14,770,209	4,546,607
Number of unique mentions	1,120,125	481,972

Table 2. Publishers collection statistics

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Publishers Collection</i>
Number of papers	16,809,266
Number of papers with at least one mention	2,893,518
Number of mentions	48,160,836
Number of unique mentions	934,704

Table 3. Papers in Publishers’ Collection

<i>Publisher</i>	<i>Number of papers with at least one mention</i>
American Association of Neurological Surgeons	7,512
American College of Physicians	1,001
American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics	8,670
American Institute of Physics	48,565
American Physical Society	9,649
American Psychiatric Association Publishing	5,171
American Society for Clinical Investigation	8,787
American Society for Microbiology	4,943
American Society of Agricultural and Biological Engineers	1,132
American Society of Civil Engineers	30,641
American Thoracic Society	2,247
Annual Reviews	8,307
BioOne	61,822
bioRxiv	33,136
Cambridge University Press	205
CSIRO Publishing	5,999
De Gruyter Open	4,603
Edinburgh University Press	6,784
eLife Sciences Publications, Ltd	1,652
Emerald Publishing Limited	55,367
Future Medicine Ltd	18,934
Hindawi	23,052
Hogrefe Publishing	8,067
Impact Journals	4,191
INFORMS	669
Institute of Electrical & Electronics Engineers	43,580
IntechOpen	1
International Union of Crystallography	21
IOS Press	3,989
MA Healthcare	8,284
Mary Ann Liebert, Inc., publishers	65,597
MDPI	14,334
MIT Press	2,544
Public Library of Science	186,313
PubMed Central Open Access	1,758,247
Royal College of Surgeons of England	1,458
Royal Society of Chemistry	73,586
SAGE Publications	358,849
SLACK Incorporated	2,801
Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers	31
Springer Nature	329,910
Taylor & Francis	607,702
The Royal Society	342
University of California Press	457
Wolters Kluwer	32,940
Total	3,852,092

Software mentions extraction

We use a NER model to extract plain-text software mentions from our corpus. The SciBERT (Beltagy et al., 2019) model has been fine-tuned on the SoftCite dataset (Du et al., 2021) to recognize mentions of software and respective version. This model achieves a 10-fold cross-

validation F1 score of 0.92. More details can be found at the address <https://github.com/chanzuckerberg/software-mention-extraction>. This model was previously used on the CORD-19 dataset (Wade & Williams, 2021).

For a part of the collection: OA PMC corpus released under free license for both commercial and non-commercial use (dataset) we performed linking and disambiguation described below.

Software mentions linking and disambiguation

There can be large variability in how a piece of software is being mentioned in text. For example, a software can be mentioned through its full name (e.g. *Statistical Package for Social Sciences*) or its acronym (e.g. *SPSS*). There can also be multiple name variations commonly accepted as referring to the same software entity (e.g. *sklearn* and *scikit-learn*). And there can be variability in how a software mention is being mentioned by researchers (eg *Image J* and *ImageJ* or *GraphPad Prism* and *GraphPad* and *Prism*). Moreover, there can be typos, either introduced by the authors (e.g. *scikits-learn*) or by parsing the XML of the papers, and there can be variability in how the NER algorithm extracts different software mentions (e.g. partial matches). If we want to assess the impact of a software entity, we need to be able to map all of the different string variations that correspond to a particular software entity together.

Our goal is to build a software entity data model and describe a software entity through its name (eg *scikit-learn*), the string variations under which this entity appears mentioned in the literature, as extracted by the NER model (e.g. *sklearn*, *Sklearn API*, *scikit-learn API*, *scikits-learn*, *Python toolbox scikit-learn*, *Scikit-Learn Library*, etc) and, ideally, a link to a repository or database, such as <https://pypi.org/project/scikit-learn>.

To achieve this, after *extracting* the software mentions from the PMC-OA corpus using the NER model, we use two additional methodologies: *disambiguation* and *linking* for the part free for commercial use (Table 1). We define disambiguation as the process of mapping various string variations of the same software entity together. Linking refers to mapping a software entity to a URL in a repository or database. We describe each of these steps in more detail in the following sections.

Software mentions disambiguation

In the PMC-OA *comm* corpus, *MATLAB*, the *R* package *limma* and *GraphPad* are each extracted by the NER model under more than 200 string variations. *BLAST*, an algorithm for comparing primary biological sequence information, has more than 500 variations extracted by the NER model. Through disambiguation, our goal is to group different string variations of the same software entity together. For instance, all the string variations for *limma* should be grouped under the *limma* software entity, all the string variations for *MATLAB* should be grouped under the *MATLAB* software entity, and so on.

Starting with a set of papers (in our case the PMC-OA *comm* corpus), we run the NER algorithm and obtain the set S of all software strings extracted from the corpus. We build a similarity matrix M containing similarity scores between pairs of strings in S . Then we break M down into distinct connected components, and run DBSCAN (Ester, Kriegel, Sander, & Xu, 1996) on each. From each connected component, we obtain clusters of strings corresponding to well-defined software entities. The final list of clusters is the union of all the clusters from each of the connected components in M . To obtain M , we use a combination of Keywords-

based synonym generation, SciCrunch synonyms retrieval and Jaro-Winkler string similarity scores. We go over our methodology in more detail below.

Keywords-based synonym generation

We query PyPi (Anonymous, 2022b), CRAN (Anonymous, 2022d) and Bioconductor (Gentleman et al., 2004) indices, which contain lists of software packages available on each of these platforms. For each software entry in each index, we look for entries in the list of all plain-text software mentions that contain the match and keywords relevant to that index. For example, once we find *limma* as an entry in the Bioconductor package, we look for other plain-text software mentions in our original list that contain the word *limma* and keywords relevant to the Bioconductor index, such as *limma R package*, *R package limma*, etc. We consider pairs retrieved this way (e.g. *limma* and *limma R package* and *limma* and *R package limma*) to be high-confidence synonyms.

SciCrunch synonyms retrieval

We query the SciCrunch API (FDI Lab, 2022a) for each of the mentions in our corpus. When queried for a particular entry, the SciCrunch API has the option of returning different variations under which that software is known. This includes mappings between acronyms and full names (eg *SPSS* and *Statistical Package for the Social Sciences*, but also mappings between different naming variations, (e. g. *BLASTN*, *NCBI BLASTN*, *Nucleotide BLAST*, *Standard Nucleotide BLAST*). This allows us to connect different naming variations of the same software together at scale.

String similarity algorithms

We use the Jaro-Winkler string similarity algorithm (Winkler & Thibaudeau, 1991) to generate similarity scores between all pairs of software mentions from the list of all plain-text software mentions extracted. Examples are shown in Table 4. We use these scores in the similarity matrix for pairs of software mentions that we didn't retrieve through keywords-based synonyms generation or through the SciCrunch API.

Table 4. Examples of software synonym pairs retrieved through Keywords synonym generation. The synonyms are strings extracted by the NER algorithm

<i>Software Mention</i>	<i>Synonym</i>
scikit-learn	scikit-learn python package
scikit-learn	scikit-learn python library
scikit-learn	scikit-learn python
scikit-learn	scikit-learn library for Python
scikit-learn	scikit-learn Python package2223
scikit-learn	scikit-learn Python package for
scikit-learn	scikit-learn Python package

Clustering

After we generate all the synonym pairs, we build our similarity matrix M . We consider synonyms retrieved through keywords-based synonym generation process to be high-confidence synonyms to the original entries. Hence, we add them to our similarity matrix with the confidence of 0.99. We are really confident in the synonym pairs retrieved from SciCrunch, so we give them the confidence of 1. For all other pairs of strings, we use the Jaro-Winkler string similarity (Winkler & Thibaudeau, 1991) values in our matrix. We only use pairs of

synonyms with a confidence ≥ 0.97 . We make this choice so that the largest connected component can fit into working memory and also to increase the confidence in the pairs of synonyms we consider. A drawback of this is that we will lose a number of pairs of synonyms. Future work could include finding ways to overcome this limitation. Our similarity matrix is described by:

$$M_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & (i, j) \in S_2 \\ 0.99, & (i, j) \in S_1 - S_2 \\ m_{ij}, & \text{otherwise, and } m_{ij} \geq 0.97 \end{cases}, \quad (1)$$

where S_1 is the set of pairs based on keywords-based generation, S_2 is the set of pairs obtained from SciCrunch, and m_{ij} is Jaro-Winkler distance. We perform additional post-processing of M in order to increase data quality for clustering. Steps we include are: assigning confidences of 1 for pairs of synonyms that are equal when stripped of digits, punctuation or copyright characters, or that have more than one word token and are equal, lowercase-insensitive. We also remove pairs that include broad terms that tend to have a lot of synonyms, such as 'R package', 'r package', or 'interface'. Full details can be found in our code.

Once we have built our similarity matrix M and post-processed it, we extract the connected components C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n of M and then run the DBSCAN (Ester et al., 1996) algorithm on each similarity matrix $M^{(n)}$ corresponding to the component number n . Computing the connected components helps us to reduce the size of the matrix we have to run the clustering algorithm on. For each $M^{(n)}$ we compute a distance matrix $D^{(n)}$ such that

$$D_{ij}^{(n)} = 1 - M_{ij}^{(n)}. \quad (2)$$

Using DBSCAN we obtain a set of clusters corresponding to each connected component in our graph. For each cluster, we select the software mention with the highest frequency in our corpus as the cluster name. Empirically, we noticed that this string variation is the most likely to be the real name of the software entity. This also corresponds to the intuitive idea of the “true software mention”.

We use the `textdistance` python package (Anonymous, 2021) to compute the Jaro-Winkler similarity scores. We use a CSR sparse matrix format for the similarity matrix and use the `connected_components` module from `scipy.sparse.csgraph` (Anonymous, 2022c) to obtain the connected components. We use the DBSCAN implementation from `sklearn.cluster` (Pedregosa et al., 2011).

Software mentions linking

Once we cluster different software string variations together, we also want to link them to the corresponding URLs. For each software mention in our corpus, we do an exact match search in the PyPI (Anonymous, 2022b), CRAN (Anonymous, 2022d) and Bioconductor (Gentleman et al., 2004) indices, as well as GitHub (Anonymous, 2022a) and SciCrunch (FDI Lab, 2022b) APIs. For PyPI, CRAN, Bioconductor and SciCrunch, we also query individual URL pages for matches we find. Combined, we obtain links, as well as additional metadata, for a number of software mentions. Because the format and type of metadata available varies across repositories, we normalize the formats to a common schema between repositories. The final metadata fields we retrieve across repositories and normalizing to contain: *source*, *package_url*, *description*, *homepage_url*, *other_urls*, *license*, *github_repo*,

github_repo_license, *exact_match*, *RRID*, *reference*. Note that not all software mentions will have all of the metadata fields present, either because there was no corresponding field in the database for that field, or the entry was empty in the database. We make the schema normalization mappings between the initial fields present in a database and the final metadata fields available in Table 5.

We map each cluster to the link to which the cluster name is pointing to. For instance, we map all the entries in the *scikit-learn* cluster to the *scikit-learn* link. For situations where the cluster name does not have an associated link, or a software mention is not mapped to a cluster, we look for an exact match link for that particular software mention itself.

Table 5. List of normalized metadata, together with definitions, for fields obtained by linking through the PyPI, CRAN, Bioconductor indices and SciCrunch and GitHub APIs.

Field	Definition
database	database the software is being mapped to
package_url	URL of the software in the database
description	description of the software in the database
github_repository	GitHub repository for the software
homepage_url	homepage for the software (retrieved from the database)
other_URLS	list of other URLs retrieved for the software from the database
reference	journal article linked to the software, identified by DOI, PMID or RRID
scicrunch_synonyms	synonyms for software retrieved from SciCrunch
resource_type	resource type according to SciCrunch
RRID	RRID for the software retrieved from SciCrunch

Dataset curation

Motivation

The NER model has an F1 score of 0.922, with a precision of 0.9063 and a recall value of 0.9385. These metrics are calculated on the SoftCite dataset (Du et al., 2021), which has been used for training the NER model. Since the PMC-OA corpus distribution is different from the one of the SoftCite Dataset, we engaged our in-house team of bio-curators to first evaluate a sample of the top 1000 plain text software mentions (by means of frequency) extracted from the PMC-OA *comm* subset. Based on this evaluation, we concluded that the Precision@1000 of the NER model “in the wild”, on the PMC-OA corpus is 79.5%. After this assessment, and in order to eliminate as much noise from the dataset as possible, we engaged our bio-curator team to curate another set of top 9000 mentions (by frequency), thereby generating a dataset of 10000 curated mentions in total. Each of the 1000 mentions was annotated by a single curator and checked by a second curator; the 9000 mentions were curated by one curator each. After excluding terms that our biocurators mark as *non-software*, we are left with 6966 mentions that meet our definition of software as shown in Tables 6, 7, and 8. We curate all three corpora: *comm*, *non_comm* and the *Publishers’ collection* datasets to exclude mentions marked by curators as *non-software*. We also make the raw datasets available, together with the curators’ labeling, and comments.

Table 6: Metrics of curated datasets. The table shows the coverage of the 10,000 curated

mentions in the PMC-OA and CZ Publishers’ Collection datasets. The curated mentions are the top 10k mentions in terms of frequency on the PMC- OA comm dataset

<i>Corpus</i>	<i>Mentions covered by the 10k dataset</i>	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>% of the set</i>
PMC-OA comm	9.03M	61.158
PMC-OA non_comm	2.67M	58.923
CZ publishers_collection	20.11M	41.766

Curation guidelines & evaluation

Our software definitions, are broadly based on the definitions used for the SoftCite dataset (Du et al., 2021), on which the NER model has been trained. We start with five different categories: *software*, *algorithm*, *database*, *web platform*, *hardware* and *other* and ask our curators to annotate the top 1000 most frequent mentions from our corpus with these categories. To facilitate the curation process, we provide for each software mention five different sentences extracted from the articles; where the sentences do not provide sufficient information about the software, the curators are asked to find background information through Google searches. The curation of the top 1000 mentions allowed us to (a) understand the variety of mentions that are present in the dataset (see Table 6) and (b) identify additional examples for each category (in particular, borderline cases) and refine the curation guidelines further.

We consider mentions in the *software* and *algorithm* categories to be true *software*, whereas mentions in the *database*, *hardware*, *web platform* and *other* categories are considered as *non-software*. Based on this human evaluation, 79.5% of 1000 mentions are evaluated as *software*, and 16.5% as *non-software*. For the remaining 4% of mentions, a distinction between software and non-software could not be made; this is either because a software name or acronym could be pointing to two different entities (labeled as *unclear*), or because the mentions extracted by the NER model were random symbols. For the evaluation of the 9000 mentions, we only ask our curators to distinguish between the main *software/non-software* categories. In the final curated dataset of 10000 software mentions, 69.66% of mentions are evaluated as *software*, 21.55% as *non-software*, and for 8.79% an evaluation could not be made.

Table 7. Expert evaluation of most frequent mentions extracted by the NER model from the PMC-OA comm dataset

<i>Category</i>	<i>Precision@1k, %</i>	<i>Precision@10k, %</i>
software	79.5	69.66
not-software	16.5	21.55
unclear	4	8.79

Inter-Annotator Agreement

We compute the Inter-Annotator Agreement (IAA) value by looking at curator evaluations on a random sample of 100 mentions from the larger sample of 1000 (Table 8). With four curators per mention, we obtain a Fleiss Kappa IAA value (Gwet, 2014) of 0.639 when only the two main categories (software/non-software) are considered, and 0.504 when the more specific five subcategories (software, algorithm, database, web platform, hardware, other) are labeled. We also compute the Krippendorff Alpha IAA (Gwet, 2014) values, which are similar: 0.686 for the two main categories and 0.523 for five subcategories (Table 9). Since we are interested in

the binary (software/non-software) differentiation, our IAA values of concern are around 0.639/0.686. We want to note that the relatively low IAA value demonstrates that this is a challenging task even for our expert curator team. The fact that the IAA value is relatively low should be interpreted as a signal for how hard it is to distinguish in some cases whether a mention is a true software or not. Specifically, it is difficult to differentiate between ‘software’ and ‘algorithm’ as these terms are often used interchangeably by authors describing their tools: the tool may be called “software” on the tool’s website but described as an “algorithm” in an article. Similarly, some online tools consist of a database and software of the same name, so there may be disagreement how curators annotate the software mention. It is also important to note that the curation relied on both the context given by 5 example sentences and background searches. The use of different sources of information can result in different annotations; this is particularly true for software mentions that consist of acronyms, have ambiguous names or share part of their name with other software and/or non-software resources.

Table 8. Expert evaluation of 1000 most frequent mentions extracted by the NER model

<i>Main Category</i>	<i>Subcategory</i>	<i>Counts</i>	<i>%</i>
Software	Software	699	69.9
Software	Algorithm	95	9.5
Non-Software	Database	40	4.0
Non-Software	Hardware	9	9
Non-Software	Web platform	13	1.3
Non-Software	Other	105	10.5
Errors	Unclear	39	3.9

Table 9: IAA curation values for the expert evaluation of the most frequent mentions extracted by the NER model from the PMC-OA comm dataset

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Five categories</i>	<i>Two categories</i>
Fleiss κ	0.504	0.639
Krippendorff α	0.523	0.686

Evaluation & results

Final dataset

The statistics of software mentions extracted from the OA-PMC comm is shown in Table 1. The results of disambiguation and linking are shown in Table 10. As seen from this table, for about 390,000 mentions we could not generate synonyms or we discarded them during post-processing. By analyzing some of these mentions, we hypothesize that they are likely to be noise or false positives. For about 720,000 mentions we were able to generate synonyms. Again, about 400,000 of the latter were too ambiguous to disambiguate. This is likely because the software mentions did not have significant synonyms (with a confidence of ≥ 0.97 during the disambiguation phase). The remaining 320,000 mentions were mapped into 97,600 unique software entities through the disambiguation algorithm. This covers 78% of all links in the dataset. Lastly, for about 185,000 mentions we were able to obtain links to GitHub, PyPI, CRAN, Bioconductor, or SciCrunch. This covers about 55% of all software-paper links.

Table 10: OA PMC comm disambiguation and linking

<i>Category</i>	<i>Mentions</i>		<i>Paper-software links</i>		<i>Notes</i>
	<i>Approx. #</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Approx. #</i>	<i>%</i>	
undisambiguated	393,057	35	731,529	8.95	no significant synonyms
undisambiguated	404,493	36.11	1,050,017	12.85	no output from clustering
disambiguated	323,561	28.88	6,384,430	78.18	97600 unique software entities
disambiguated <i>and</i> linked	185,427	16.55	4,555,476	55.78	
total unique mentions	1,120,111	100	8,165,976	100	

Disambiguation

Perhaps the biggest challenge in disambiguation is that we don't have curated labels to learn from. Our methodology, based on DBSCAN (Ester et al., 1996), is unsupervised. We engaged our biocurators for evaluation of the results.

We created a set of 5884 pairs of generated synonyms coming from 104 unique software mentions for manual curation. This dataset was generated from an initial iteration of the disambiguation algorithm. We asked our curation team to label each synonym pair with one of the following categories:

Exact: synonym is an exact match of the assigned Software mention

Narrow: synonym is a child term

Not Synonym: synonym is an unrelated software or other term

The *Exact* category includes all mentions that can unambiguously be assigned to the software mention, including partial terms, typos, variations on spelling (upper/lower case, space, hyphen etc), and acronyms. Reference numbers in the article are often erroneously added to the software synonym; these are also labeled as *Exact*. Versions of software are annotated as *Narrow*. Partial versions are also included here, for example "Autodock Vina1" for "Autodock Vina1.1.2". It is worth noting that synonyms representing software versions can be challenging to distinguish from synonyms which include the reference number (e.g. "Autodock Vina19" where 19 is the reference number in the article mentioning the software). Synonyms of software tools that have common names pose another challenge for this task: for example, it is time-consuming to work out whether "ClusterM" is a true synonym for a version of the software tool "Cluster" or represents a completely distinct software called ClusterM. We considered pairs that fall into either of *Exact* or *Narrow* categories to be true synonyms. Composition of this curated labels is under (Table 11).

We used this dataset and the labels assigned by our curators to validate our clustering technique, by computing the Precision, Recall and the F1 score for generated pairs of synonyms. We chose the hyperparameters that gave the highest metrics on this curated dataset. Our best model had an F1 score of 0.704, with a Precision of 0.954 and Recall of 0.558.

Table 11: Disambiguation Evaluation. Description of the dataset used for evaluating disambiguation. Labels were assigned by our curation team on 5886 pairs of generated synonyms coming from 103 unique software mentions

<i>Synonym Pair Label</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>%</i>
Correct - Exact	3,147	53.465
Correct - Narrow	1,094	18.586
Incorrect	668	13.484
Unclear	45	0.908
Not software	930	15.805

As an example, on Figure 1 we show the cluster "scikit-learn" after the disambiguation.

Scikit-Learn	Sci-Kit learn
scikit-learn Python	sklearn0
scikit-learn	Python Scikit Learn
Scikit learn	Scikit-Learn Python Library

sklearn	Python scikit_learn
scikit-learn Python library	2scikit-learn
Scikit-learn	SCikit-learn
Sklearn	SCIKIT-learn
Python scikit-learn	Scikit-Learn
scikit learn	Python Sci-kit learn
scikit-learn	Python package Scikit-learn
Scikit-learn	scikit-Learn
Scikit-Learn Python	Scikit-Learn Python package
scikit-learn81	scikit-learn Python Library
SciKit-Learn	sklearn python package
sklearn Python	sci-kit learn Python package
SkLearn	Python scikit learn package
scikit -learn	skLearn
Python Scikit-Learn	Scikit-learn python
Scikit-Learn®	scikitslearn
Python sklearn library	scikit-learn Python package for
scikit.learn	Python sci-kit learn
Scikits-learn	Scikit-Learn Python
Sci-kit-learn	scikit - learn Python library
scikit-learn Python3 package

Figure 1: Sample of Disambiguation results for the software entity scikit-learn. There are a total of 124 unique string variations extracted by the NER model that are mapped to the scikit-learn software entity through disambiguation.

Linking

As with disambiguation, we don't have any labeled data to evaluate our linking, so we engage our team of biocurators for feedback. We provide our biocurators with 50 software mentions, together with the generated links. Based on biocurator feedback, 54% the generated links are correct, 6% are incorrect, and for 40% it is unclear whether the link is correct. Most notably, 39/40 mentions for which the link is unclear are retrieved from GitHub and only one is linked through PyPI, Bioconductor, CRAN and SciCrunch. This happens because GitHub is a resource that is not curated, so having an exact match on a software name in GitHub does not guarantee that it will be linking to the actual software. Anyone can upload software in GitHub and name it as they wish. A number of repositories we evaluated were empty, or contained too little information to be able to decide for sure if the linking was correct. When we consider the evaluation only of links retrieved through PyPI, Bioconductor, CRAN and SciCrunch, the accuracy improves considerably: 93.33% of links are correct and 0.6% are incorrect, 0% unclear. This suggests that linking software through these four repositories through an exact match is likely to give correct links. We note, however, that the sample size for this evaluation is quite small, and it is possible that results might change with a larger sample. Linking coverage is shown in Table 12, and linking statistics in Table 13. The metadata statistics is shown in Table 14.

Table 12. Linking Coverage

<i>Repository</i>	<i>Number of linked mentions</i>	<i>%</i>
GitHub API	1,55,506	64.39
SciCrunch API	43,817	18.14

<i>Repository</i>	<i>Number of linked mentions</i>	<i>%</i>
CRAN	20,202	8.36
PyPI	14,154	5.86
Bioconductor	7,801	3.23

Table 13. Linking Evaluation on a sample dataset of 50 generated links to PyPI, CRAN, Bioconductor, GitHub and SciCrunch

<i>Link label</i>	<i>All links</i>		<i>Excluding GitHub</i>	
	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>%</i>
correct	27	54	14	93.33
unclear	20	40	1	6.66
incorrect	3	6	0	0

Code & data availability

We make the dataset, as well as all intermediate files available at <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.6wwpzgn2c> under a CC0 license (Istrate et al., 2022b). All the code used for extraction, disambiguation and linking, as well as instructions on how to reproduce the results and some starter code is available at a GitHub repository <https://github.com/chanzuckerberg/software-mentions> under the MIT license with the permanent snapshot at (Istrate et al., 2022a).

Table 14. Metadata Fields Statistics for the mentions linked to a repository. Synonyms retrieved through disambiguation that might link to the same entry are not counted

<i>Normalized metadata field</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>%</i>
package_url	1,49,015	100
github_repo	1,43,834	96.52
description	1,160,71	77.89
homepage_url	36,306	24.36
github_repo_license	39,464	26.48
reference	22,134	14.85
RRID	18,766	12.59
other_urls	18,766	12.59
license	13,485	9.04

Discussion

The dataset we make available is, to our knowledge, the largest dataset of software mentions in the scientific literature currently available. In this section, we go over some of the lessons learned in building a dataset this large, as well as limitations of current work. We offer a view on opportunities for further work in the Next Steps section.

Extraction

An important feature of our extraction is the maximal preservation of the context of the software mention. We keep the sentence from which the mention was extracted as well as the reference to the unit (section, caption, abstract) from which it was extracted. This helped in the curation. This may facilitate more deep reprocessing of the dataset the future, including better disambiguation and linking. This feature became available because we had the access to the structure of the papers, using their XML representation. Many other studies, for example,

(Lopez, Du, Cohoon, & Howison, 2021), process the text extracted from PDF, which does not show the structure. The current tendency of the publishers to keep the archival copies of the papers in the XML format is probably one of the best things that happened to the field of data mining from scholarly documents.

Software name variability in the literature

The goal of building a comprehensive dataset of software mentions in the literature is to be able to assess software impact through informal citations. One of the main challenges is the variability under which a software can be mentioned, or 'informally cited' in a paper. Some of this variability is to be expected, such as differences between using the fullname or the acronym of a software (eg *SPSS* and *Statistical Package for Social Sciences*), authors using various software name variations (eg *SPSS Statistics*, *IBM SPSS*) or typos.

But probably the biggest string variability comes from how the NER model extracts software from text. For instance, the NER model might extract the following mentions: *R package limma*, *limma R package*, *Limma*, all pointing out to the same software.

Lastly, there is variability coming from typos that are occurring either due to the authors or because of XML parsing. If we want to truly get the impact of a particular piece of software, we need to be able to map all of these software naming variations to the same software entity.

Disambiguation

In order to map software variations to the same software entity, we built a software disambiguation model. We describe the model, based largely on string similarity algorithms and clustering techniques, above. Note that through this model, we are only able to disambiguate 28.88% mentions that constitute 78.18% of paper-software links. The other mentions either have no significant synonyms or are too ambiguous to disambiguate (Table 10). We propose this as a baseline model. Because the raw data is available, more sophisticated disambiguation algorithms can be employed. We want to note that the main challenge in disambiguating mentions in a dataset this large is the lack of labels, which means that the disambiguation tasks would have to be unsupervised. This poses challenges in terms of evaluation. We evaluated our disambiguation method using our biocuration team, which evaluated 5884 synonym pairs that we subsequently used to validate our model. The other challenge in using unsupervised methods, such as clustering, on a dataset this large, is the generation of distance matrices that would fit into working memory.

We also want to note that we experimented with using transformer-based models to generate embeddings for software mentions and compute similarity scores between pairs of strings by using the dot product or cosine similarity. We obtained unsatisfactory results creating similarity scores in this way. Pairs of strings that are semantically different than each other ended up having similar embeddings. This makes sense, as transformer-based models compute representational encodings for sequences based on context. It is possible that packages that are similar in some way, like *sklearn* and *scipy*, appear in similar contexts, and hence, will have similar embeddings. We hypothesize that the level of context around how a particular software is mentioned in a research paper is not granular enough to allow the computation of an embedding specific enough to differentiate that software from other similar, but different softwares. Basically, the language (and hence context) which authors use to mention *sklearn* is likely to be very similar to the language authors use to mention *scipy*. It makes sense that their embeddings will be close in n -dimensional space. We hypothesize that being able to use the context around a mention would, however, be useful for ambiguous cases when two different

software can have the same name, or acronyms. This would be an interesting area of further work.

Use cases

As a philanthropic organization supporting and building technology to serve the computational needs of biomedical scientists, we rely on data on scientific software to inform our programmatic activities (CZI, 2022b; Sofroniew & Taraborelli, 2019) and technology strategy (CZI, 2022a). In this section we discuss a couple of ways the dataset has already been used in our work at the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative prior to the public release.

Trends in imaging

The Chan Zuckerberg Initiative considers imaging to be one of the key technologies in our effort to develop science and technologies to measure human biology in action (CZI, 2021b, 2021a). To fund this area more efficiently and support the relevant computational tools, we needed to understand the methods used in the field and the penetration of open-source ones, in particular.

Modern biomedical imaging is significantly computational in nature. Thus we were able to use our data to identify the papers using various imaging software. We used publication data to get the time trends and the change of relative market share for both open and closed source imaging software.

Penetration of single-cell methods in biomedicine

Single-cell methods are another key area of biomedical technology supported by CZI (CZI, 2021a). To better focus our efforts, we needed data on the penetration of single-cell methods in the clinical research literature. The software used for analysis of single cell data is specific, so mention of this software in a paper can be a good marker of the usage of single cell methods. We were able to get a subset of papers that used single cell methods, and to estimate the penetration of these methods in the different biomedical subfields.

Other usage

We would like to note that the use cases mentioned in this section were also recognized by other people, for example, Wikidata Scholia project (Nielsen, Mietchen, & Willighagen, 2017). There are many other interesting questions, like the identifying the most influential authors, co-uses etc. (Nielsen et al., 2017). We hope our dataset can be used by projects like Scholia and intend to integrate our results with Wikidata in the future releases.

Next steps

We believe that there are a number of exciting questions this dataset can help answer. To start with, we can look into what the most used software is in a particular field (e.g. *neurodegeneration, single-cell biology, imaging*). We can go a step further and try to understand what the software is used for. Potential ideas include getting insights from paper or sentence topics, MESH terms, author-provided paper keywords, or information found in the sentence in which the software is being mentioned (note that we make this available). We can also start looking at differences between how software usage differs between particular fields, if any. Furthermore, we can explore measures of impact for software, whether those are number of informal citations (such as software mentions), or more sophisticated models. For instance, since we are now able to connect papers and software entities in an underlying graph, we can start exploring with graph-based models for impact. One particularly exciting idea would be to extend the notion of Eigenfactor, which has been proposed measure impact for journals and authors, to software. Other potential areas of further research include looking into open-access policies of most used or impactful software or exploring differences in how software usage

varies over time. Last but not least, we can look into the impact of particular pieces of software and assess their impact.

The approach we took in this paper was to use an NER model to collect software string variations from a corpus of papers, and then disambiguate and link these mentions into clusters of software entities using DBSCAN (Ester et al., 1996) and a similarity matrix we built. Using this methodology, we were able to disambiguate about a third of the total number of unique mentions in our dataset, which covers about 78% of the total paper-software links. This means that we are losing information from the rest of the total number of mentions in our dataset. Future work can include improving the disambiguation algorithms to be able to cluster a larger percentage of our dataset under particular software entities.

For linking, we used an exact match search on a software mention in some of the most used software repositories, such as PyPI, CRAN, Bioconductor, SciCrunch and GitHub. We want to acknowledge that there are limitations in this approach. For instance, there can be different software having the same acronyms, or different entities, whether software, databases, hardware or platforms with the same name. Moreover, in repositories that are not curated, such as GitHub, anyone can post a piece of software under whatever name they want. Being able to distinguish which is the true link for a piece of context would most likely require being able to look at the context in the text around a piece of software is being mentioned. Since we make the sentences in which a software mention appears available, we believe linking algorithms based on context are worth exploring. Improving the quality of linking software mentions to corresponding URLs in repositories or databases is an interesting area for further research.

Conclusion

We created one of the largest dataset of software mentions in the literature. For a subset of the data we used string similarity algorithms and unsupervised clustering techniques to disambiguate the software mentions into distinct software entities. We used a linking algorithm to connect the mentions to URLs in the PyPI, CRAN, Bioconductor indices and the SciCrunch and GitHub APIs. We make the dataset available to the community and believe there are a number of exciting next steps. It is our hope that this new resource helps foster new insights about software usage and impact in the literature.

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